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Utilization of Video Graphics in Teaching Hairdressing and Performance of Grade Eleven Students

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Abstract

Since the evolution of technology, it created a growing importance in the education sector. The use of video graphics or multimedia tools becomes a useful instrument in learning and teaching in the education industry. This study determined the correlation between the utilization of video graphics in teaching Hairdressing and the students' performance. A descriptive method of research was applied to accomplish this study. A total of thirty-three (33) Grade Eleven TVL students served as the respondents of this study. The researcher used a survey questionnaire in checklist format as the main research instrument to gather needed data. Statistics tools such as mean, standard deviation mean scores, and frequencies were used. The significance was tested at the 0.05 probability level. Based on the data collected, the perception of the students to the utilization of video graphics in teaching Hairdressing has an overall interpretation of "highly observed". It was revealed that there is a significant difference between the pre and post-test exams, considering the delivery of the lesson, teacher's mastery, efficiency, and feedback. The results indicate no significant relationship except for efficiency and performing hair treatment, audio, and post-service activities. The results also showed a positive learning development in terms of lesson adaptation through pre- and post-test scores and performance scores based on what the students knew before and after exposure to the video graphics.

Keywords: *hairdressing, hair and scalp treatment, performance skills, video graphics*

Introduction

Technology has revolutionized various aspects of life, notably enhancing the education sector through tools like video graphics. Video graphics have become invaluable in teaching and learning, making information exchange more efficient. Dr. Ethel Agnes P. Valenzuela highlights the need to embrace digital advancements to address educational challenges (Amadora, 2020). Teachers use technology to create engaging lessons and bridge the global achievement gap (Hunter & Jordan, 2009).

Competency-based learning, especially in Technical and Vocational Education (TVL), focuses on equipping students with practical skills aligned with industry demands. This approach has become popular for improving students' learning outcomes (Grafton et al., 2018; Smith & Johnson, 2016). Experiential learning through real-world projects and simulations is emphasized to prepare students for the workforce.

Instructional tools, including video graphics, support competency-based learning by providing interactive and personalized learning experiences (Dziuban & Moskal, 2020). These tools enable self-paced learning and enhance engagement, collaboration, and skill mastery (Franklin et al., 2016; Hew & Cheung, 2014). This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of video graphics in teaching Hairdressing to Grade 11 students at General Mariano Alvarez Technical High School. By analyzing student outcomes and feedback, the research seeks to offer practical recommendations for integrating video graphics into competency-based learning.

Students today, primarily Millennials and Generation Z, are drawn to smartphones and electronic gadgets for both entertainment and education. Educators have leveraged this interest to develop new teaching methods, especially during the pandemic's blended learning era. General Mariano Alvarez Technical High School, offering TVL courses like Hairdressing, aligned its curriculum with TESDA standards to achieve a National Certificate. Video demonstrations have proven effective in enhancing students' understanding and mastery of skills in competency-based learning settings (Dziuban & Moskal, 2020; Oztok & Brett, 2018). Video-based learning supports diverse learning styles and allows for self-paced study, making it a powerful tool in modern education (Ljubojevic et al., 2014).

Platforms like YouTube and Facebook facilitate the sharing of educational videos, enabling global access to instructional content (O'Bannon & Beard, 2015; Junco, 2015). Research indicates that video graphics foster engagement, community, and real-world application of skills, aligning well with competency-based learning principles (Junco, 2015; Hew & Cheung, 2014). This study explores the impact of video graphics on student performance in Hairdressing, aiming to enhance competency-based education.

Research Objectives

The objective of this study is to explore how online platforms facilitate knowledge acquisition, collaborative learning, and learner engagement, particularly through the use of video graphics in competency-based education. By examining the integration of video graphics in the teaching of Hairdressing, this research aims to provide valuable insights into their impact on students' written performance and practical skills demonstration. The findings will help educators understand how video graphics can enhance learning experiences, enabling students to excel in acquiring, developing, and performing various competencies. Ultimately, this study aspires to offer practical recommendations for effectively incorporating video graphics into competency-based learning environments, thereby empowering both educators and students to achieve higher levels of success in the educational process.

Methodology

This study utilized an experimental research design, a scientific approach that investigates cause-and-effect relationships between variables by manipulating one or more independent variables and observing their effects on a dependent variable while controlling for other potential influencing factors. Specifically, a pre-and post-test design was employed, assessing participants on the dependent variable both before and after the treatment to measure any changes and later evaluate the effect of the independent variable.

Data was collected through surveys, written exams, and skill performance assessments using rubrics. This allowed the study to describe the utilization of video graphics in teaching Hairdressing and assess students' competency performance after viewing the prepared videos. The correlational aspect of the study analyzed the associations between the use of video graphics in teaching and competency-based learning outcomes, identifying any potential relationships between these variables.

By adopting this research design, the study offered valuable insights into the role of video graphics as an instructional tool in Grade 11 students' competency-based learning journey. It also identified potential factors contributing to their academic success and overall learning progress. Additionally, the research examined the profile of the students, including their family's occupation and income, to understand their capacity to access video graphics via devices.

This study also explored the development of new possibilities and learning opportunities with the use of technology in competency-based learning. These were identified through students' pre-test, post-test, and skills performance on the competencies, providing a comprehensive understanding of how video graphics can enhance the educational experience and contribute to student success.

Results and Discussion

This study utilized self-made video graphics as a teaching tool in hairdressing and find out the performance of the grade eleven students. At first, the researcher hypothesized that there is no significant difference in the pretest and post-test scores of the students in Hair and Scalp Treatment, and the competency performance in Hair and Scalp Treatment is not significantly related to the video graphics applications; and the features of video graphics. The research uses experimental research design to find out the cause and effect of video graphics utilization, and it seeks to offer valuable insights into the role of video graphics as an instructional tool in Grade 11 students' competency-based learning journey. This study used a purposive sampling technique to gather the thirty-three (33) respondents of this study, Grade eleven and of the TVL strand. Percentages, frequencies, weighted average and scores, t-test, and Pearson-r correlation were used to analyze the data from a survey questionnaire as a tool, pre-and post-tests, and performance rubrics.

Table 1. *Significant Relationship of the Respondent's Performance in Hairdressing Competencies and video graphics application; and features of the video graphics*

Hairdressing Competencies	Prepare client	Perform hair treatment	Perform scalp treatment	Perform post service activities
Video Graphics Application				
Delivery of lesson	0.039	0.039	0.064	0.142
Mastery of the lesson	0.159	0.212	0.042	0.251
Efficiency	0.012	.353*	0.100	0.071
Feedback	0.274	0.266	0.148	0.001
Features of Video Graphics				
Lesson content	0.290	0.114	0.117	0.238
Audio	0.217	0.083	0.086	.390*
Visual	0.009	0.279	0.178	0.182
Accessibility	0.039	0.013	0.010	0.061

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table above determined that the implementation of video graphics as a teaching tool in hairdressing demonstrated a huge development between the pre-and post-test exams in terms of lesson delivery, teacher mastery, efficiency, and student feedback. It revealed that the pre-test and post-test scores of the respondents improved after using the video graphics.

Results also revealed that the efficiency and audio aspects of the video graphics have a minimal significant relationship. Other variables have no evidence of a significant impact on how well people perform tasks related to hair and scalp treatment.

Conclusions

Based on the above findings, the following conclusions were drawn. This study found important findings on the use of video graphics in hairdressing education. The first finding was that students' performance on the pre- and post-test tests significantly improved, suggesting that the use of video graphics improves teacher feedback, course delivery, and overall efficiency on the part of the teacher giving the lesson. Furthermore, this discovered a strong association between the effectiveness of video graphics and hair treatment

competency, indicating their potential as an influential medium for experiential education achieving the required competency. As a result, learners benefit greatly from having watched video demonstrations before to doing tasks or performing the incompetencies, as it helps them better understand the aspects of the activity and enhances their performance overall.

The following are recommended: These findings led the researcher to recommend that teachers who are teaching TVL specializations may consider creating and using video graphics as instructional tools in teaching different TVL specializations to develop student's knowledge and skills. Considering the result of the study, it may be suggested that teachers may use video graphics as a teaching tool that contributes to enhancing the knowledge and skills development of the learners. It may be recommended that educators continue to develop instructional materials that will support the teaching and learning process. Researchers use this study as a basis and may include interactive features such as quizzes, simulations, and hands-on activities that can reinforce learning and promote skill acquisition. The researcher also recommends conducting further studies to validate or enhance this study for the changing needs of the learners. The researcher also recommends that school administrators provide technical support and assistance on the implementation of the video graphics application not only for the Hairdressing but also for other existing localized video graphics created by teachers.

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